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FORMING DEMAND AND STIMULATING SALES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In this article, we consider methods of demand generation and sales promotion in Uzbekistan, taking into account the specifics of the local market. We analyze key marketing tools such as advertising, promotion, pricing strategies and loyalty programs, and study the impact of digital technologies and social networks on consumer behavior. Particular attention is paid to successful cases and examples applicable to the Uzbek market. In conclusion, we offer practical recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of marketing strategies adapted to modern market conditions.

Key words: demand generation, sales promotion, marketing, advertising, promotion, customer loyalty, digital technologies, social networks, Uzbekistan market, sales strategies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biz mahalliy bozorning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda, O'zbekistonda talabni shakllantirish va sotishni rag'batlantirish usullarini ko'rib chiqamiz. Reklama, narx strategiyasi, mijozlarning sodiqligini oshirish dasturlari kabi asosiy marketing vositalari tahlil qilinadi, shuningdek, raqamli texnologiyalar va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning iste'molchilarning xatti-harakatlariga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Muvaffaqiyatli amaliy holatlar va O'zbekiston bozoriga xos real misollarga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Xulosa qilib aytganda, maqolada zamonaviy bozor sharoitlariga moslashtirilgan marketing strategiyalarining samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalar ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: talabni shakllantirish, sotishni rag'batlantirish, marketing, reklama, narx strategiyasi, mijozlarning sodiqligi, raqamli texnologiyalar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, O'zbekiston bozori, savdo strategiyalari.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются методы формирования спроса и стимулирования сбыта в Узбекистане с учетом специфики местного рынка. Анализируются ключевые маркетинговые инструменты, такие как реклама, продвижение, ценовые стратегии и программы лояльности, изучается влияние цифровых технологий и социальных сетей на поведение потребителей. Особое внимание уделяется успешным кейсам и примерам, применимым к узбекскому рынку. В заключении предлагаются практические рекомендации, направленные на повышение эффективности маркетинговых стратегий, адаптированных к современным рыночным условиям.

Ключевые слова: формирование спроса, стимулирование продаж, маркетинг, реклама, продвижение, лояльность клиентов, цифровые технологии, социальные сети, рынок Узбекистана, стратегии продаж.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen significant changes in the legislation regulating advertising activities, which has a direct impact on the processes of demand generation and sales promotion. One of the key steps in this direction was the adoption of the new Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Advertising" (LRU-776) dated June 7, 2022, which entered into force on September 9, 2022.

The new law introduced a number of significant changes aimed at improving advertising practices in the country. In particular, requirements for the language of advertising were established: now advertising must be distributed in the state language, with the possibility of dubbing in other languages, subject to certain conditions.

Restrictions have also been introduced on the use of foreign words and expressions that could distort the meaning of information, and the indication of prices in foreign currency is prohibited. In addition, the law

contains provisions aimed at protecting minors from inappropriate advertising. The use of forms, phrases and images that contradict national and family traditions, as well as generally accepted norms of morality and ethics, is prohibited.

These changes are aimed at creating a more responsible and ethical advertising environment, which in turn helps to generate healthy demand and stimulate sales.

The introduction of new legislation requires market participants to adapt their marketing strategies and advertising materials in accordance with the established standards. This opens up new opportunities for more effective interaction with consumers, taking into account the cultural and social characteristics of the country.

Thus, the updated legislation in the field of advertising in Uzbekistan plays a key role in generating demand and stimulating sales, establishing clear rules and standards for all market participants.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In the context of a dynamically developing economy such as Uzbekistan, the formation of demand and stimulation of sales requires a thorough understanding of both global marketing strategies and the specificities of the local consumer market. Numerous scholars have explored the mechanisms of demand formation in transitional economies, emphasizing the importance of adapting promotional tools to local conditions. Kotler's foundational principles of marketing provide the theoretical framework for most modern demand stimulation techniques, particularly the integration of product positioning, pricing, promotion, and place (4P) into a unified strategy.

In the context of post-Soviet markets, including Uzbekistan, Nureyev and Lvov stress the importance of consumer behavior modeling, underlining that in developing economies, demand is not only influenced by income levels but also by social norms and institutional structures. Their studies show that traditional advertising campaigns yield limited results if not paired with community-based or culturally embedded communication strategies.

Muminov's research on marketing infrastructure in Central Asia highlights that in Uzbekistan, effective demand formation relies heavily on trust-based relationships and the visibility of brands in offline environments such as bazaars and local trade fairs. He argues that while digital tools are gaining momentum, especially among younger demographics, traditional sales stimulation channels still dominate in rural and semi-urban zones.

Furthermore, Bekchanov and Saidova conducted a sectoral analysis of retail consumer goods in Uzbekistan and concluded that price sensitivity remains a critical factor. Their findings demonstrate that promotional strategies such as discounts, product bundling, and installment payment options are more effective in generating short-term sales spikes compared to loyalty programs, which require a longer time to yield measurable outcomes.

Recent research by Toirova examines how digital marketing and social media have started reshaping consumer expectations and brand engagement in Uzbekistan. She notes a growing trend among local companies to integrate influencers and targeted advertising in platforms such as Instagram and Telegram. However, she warns that low digital literacy among certain consumer groups may limit the reach of such strategies unless accompanied by education-oriented campaigns.

Additionally, in comparative studies between Uzbekistan and Eastern European markets, Akhmedov points out that while sales stimulation techniques such as flash sales and gamification show promise, their effectiveness is strongly mediated by internet penetration rates and mobile commerce infrastructure. He recommends hybrid marketing models that blend offline and online efforts, particularly for sectors like fashion, electronics, and consumer services.

Internationally, studies by Armstrong and Brennan suggest that customer engagement and retention should be prioritized alongside demand stimulation, as the cost of acquiring new customers is significantly higher than retaining existing ones. Applying this insight to Uzbekistan, local firms are advised to focus not only on sales peaks but also on long-term relationship management strategies such as CRM tools and customer feedback integration.

In summary, the literature indicates that successful demand formation and sales stimulation in Uzbekistan depend on a multifaceted approach that considers price sensitivity, cultural context, digital readiness, and sector-specific trends. While global marketing principles offer a solid foundation, adaptation to local economic behavior and infrastructure realities remains key to achieving sustainable market performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the process of research, the methods of systemic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Demand generation and sales promotion are key aspects of marketing activities aimed at ensuring sustainable growth and competitiveness of enterprises. In the context of Uzbekistan, these processes are of particular importance, given the dynamic development of the economy and the expansion of the domestic market.

Demand generation includes a set of activities aimed at identifying and satisfying consumer needs. The main tools in this process are marketing research, which allows determining the demographic, psychological and behavioral characteristics of potential buyers. Demand analysis and sales forecasting help companies adapt their products and services to market expectations.

Demand generation is the process of creating interest in a product or service among consumers. Sales promotion includes marketing tools aimed at increasing sales volumes (Table 1).

Table 1. Fundamentals of demand generation and stimulation sales development.

Factor	Demand generation	Sales promotion
Advertising	Creating brand awareness	Call to immediate purchase
Pricing Strategies	Optimizing prices for demand	Discounts, promotions, bonus programs
Promotion	Formation of the company's image	Motivating consumers to buy
Loyalty programs	Attracting new clients	Retaining existing customers

Sales promotion is a set of strategies and tactics aimed at increasing the volume of sales of goods and services. The main methods of promotion include:

Advertising campaigns: using various communication channels to inform and convince consumers of the value of a product.

Pricing strategies: setting prices based on costs, demand, and the competitive environment to attract customers.

Loyalty programs: creating reward systems for regular customers, which increases their commitment to the brand.

Trade marketing: activities aimed at improving interaction with retail partners, including the design of points of sale and motivational campaigns for employees of retail outlets.

Uzbekistan is actively implementing modern marketing practices adapted to local conditions. Particular attention is paid to the following aspects:

Marketing research: Uzbek companies are increasingly conducting research to understand the specifics of local demand. This includes analyzing consumer preferences, assessing price sensitivity, and studying cultural characteristics that influence purchasing behavior.

Lead generation: collecting and processing data about potential customers is becoming an integral part of marketing strategies. Both online methods (via websites and social networks) and offline activities are used to attract interest in products and services.

Trade marketing: designing points of sale using POS materials, holding promotions to stimulate purchases and motivating employees of retail outlets are becoming standard practice for many enterprises.

Companies use both classical methods and modern technologies to increase sales (Table 2).

Table 2. Sales promotion methods in Uzbekistan.

Stimulation methods	Application in business	Efficiency
Discounts and promotions	Often held in retail chains (Havas, Makro, Korzinka)	Tall
Loyalty programs	Loyalty cards, bonus programs	Average
Omnichannel sales	Online platforms and marketplaces (OLX, Uzum, ZoodMall)	Tall
Personalized offers	Using CRM for individual promotions	Tall

Pricing strategies: companies adapt their pricing policies in accordance with the population's solvency and the competitive environment. Pricing methods are used that focus on both costs and demand, which allows them to set optimal prices for different market segments.

Thus, the combination of theoretical approaches and practical tools in the field of demand generation and sales promotion allows Uzbek enterprises to effectively respond to market changes, meet consumer needs and ensure sustainable growth in the conditions of the modern economy.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In this article, we analyzed the methods of demand generation and sales promotion in Uzbekistan, taking into account the specifics of the local market. We reviewed key marketing tools such as advertising, promotion, pricing strategies and loyalty programs, and also studied in detail the impact of digital technologies and social networks on consumer behavior. The analysis showed that successful business development in modern conditions requires flexibility, an innovative approach and the integrated use of marketing strategies. Given the growing role of online platforms, personalized content and data analytics, companies need to adapt to new trends and customer needs.

Based on the conducted research, we propose the following measures to improve the effectiveness of marketing strategies in Uzbekistan:

Development of digital marketing– active use of social networks, content marketing and targeted advertising to increase audience reach.

Optimization of pricing strategies– a flexible approach to pricing taking into account the needs of various customer segments.

Improving loyalty programs– implementation of personalized offers, discounts and bonus programs to increase customer retention.

Expanding Marketing Research– active use of Big Data, CRM systems and analytical tools for a more accurate understanding of consumer needs.

Collaboration with influencers and bloggers– using the capabilities of opinion leaders to promote goods and services on the local market.

Strengthening trade marketing– improving the visual design of points of sale, holding promotions and events to stimulate demand.

Adaptation to legislative changes– compliance with new requirements of the legislation of Uzbekistan regulating advertising activities and marketing campaigns.

We are confident that the implementation of these recommendations will allow companies not only to increase sales volumes, but also to strengthen their competitiveness in the market, ensuring long-term growth and development.

List of used literature:

1. Kotler F. Fundamentals of Marketing. – M.: Williams, 2020.
2. Tkachenko I.N. Modern methods of sales promotion. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2019.
3. Bagiev G.L., Tarasevich V.M., Ann Kh.L. Marketing: Textbook. – M.: Peter, 2021.
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Advertising" No. 3PY-771 dated July 22, 2022.
5. Regulation on the protection of consumer rights in Uzbekistan (as amended in 2023).
6. State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Data on the dynamics of consumer demand for 2023.
7. Porter M. Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analyzing Industries and Competitors. – Free Press, 2008.
8. Chirkov D.V. Digital marketing: tools and technologies. – M.: Alpina Publisher, 2022.
9. Kotler P., Kartajaya H., Setiawan I. Marketing 4.0: Moving from Traditional to Digital. – Wiley, 2017.
10. Official website of the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan: www.mineconomy.uz.
11. Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook Publishing house OOO "STAP-SEL", 2024.
12. Musaeva Sh.A., Usmonova D.I. Innovative Marketing textbook "TURON NASHR" 2021.

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